

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

EFFECTIVENESS AND IMPROVEMENT OF RUNNING TECHNIQUE IN TRACK AND FIELD

Omonov Jahongir Orzumurod o'g'li

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, 1st Year Student of the Faculty of Physical Education

Annotation:

This article emphasizes the significant role of physical education, particularly athletics, in enhancing students' overall health, physical fitness, and preparedness for labor and national defense. It focuses on sprint running as a key component of athletics, analyzing its techniques, stages (start, acceleration, running, and finish), and their impact on physical development. The article highlights the importance of proper technique, biomechanical efficiency, and training methods for improving performance in short-distance running. It also discusses current scientific research and training innovations in the field, underlining the importance of effective methodology for sprinter development.

Key words: Physical education, athletics, sprint running, technique, acceleration, start, finish, physical fitness, biomechanical efficiency, training methods, short-distance running, performance improvement.

Physical education plays an important role in strengthening students' overall health, improving their level of physical fitness, and developing their capacity for labor activity and national defense. From this perspective, athletics holds special significance as one of the key areas that supports comprehensive physical development. This sport guides students toward a healthy lifestyle, enhances their physical qualities, and helps them achieve a high level of physical preparedness. In particular, the areas of athletics such as walking, running, jumping, throwing, and combined events have a diverse and positive impact on students' bodies and serve as a crucial factor in developing their physical potential.

Running is one of the natural forms of human movement and is considered one of the most common types of physical activity. In many sports (such as football, basketball, tennis, and others), running plays an essential role as a core movement component. As a fundamental part of athletics, running includes various disciplines that contribute to strengthening the physical condition of the human body and supporting overall development.

During running, nearly all muscle groups of the body become engaged, the cardiovascular and respiratory systems become more active, and metabolism accelerates. Additionally, regular running helps strengthen a person's willpower, develops the ability to distribute strength and energy properly, overcome obstacles, maintain balance, and adapt to environmental conditions. Thus, running is not only an important form of physical activity, but also an effective means of strengthening health and supporting comprehensive physical development of the human body.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Nowadays, many coaches emphasize that sprint running technique possesses a highly individual nature. In addition to the athlete's biomechanical characteristics, it also depends on their individual physiological capabilities and the level of speed they can achieve. However, this does not negate the existence of optimal technical elements in sprint running that are common to all. On the contrary, ongoing research is being conducted to continuously improve these elements and enhance their effectiveness.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

Experienced coaches and young researchers are consistently studying international standards for organizing sports training, the practical experience of leading coaches, and modern approaches. These studies aim to maximize athletes' physical preparedness and improve competition results.

It is well known that short-distance running in athletics is one of the most popular sports disciplines worldwide. With sports performance improving year by year, the effective organization of training sessions for sprinters, optimal distribution of workloads, and the refinement of methodological approaches are gaining increasing importance. For this reason, leading scientists and specialists around the world are developing innovative methods for training short-distance runners.

Serious scientific research has also been conducted in Uzbekistan in this area. In particular, E.R. Andris, R.Q. Qudratov, N.T. To'xtaboyev, and K.T. Shakirjonova have paid special attention in their studies to the correct teaching of technique and the use of effective tools and methods in training sessions. Their scientific work and methodological approaches play an important role in the training process of sprinters.

Thus, scientific research and practical experience in the field of athletics are of great significance for improving sports performance and organizing training processes effectively.

RESULTS

To analyze sprint running technique, the following main stages are conditionally identified:

Start

Acceleration phase

Running over the distance

Finish

Start. In short-distance running, according to competition rules, the crouch start technique is used. In this technique, the use of starting blocks helps improve the quality of the athlete's run. The use of a crouch start contributes to achieving maximum acceleration.

The placement of the starting blocks is an individual matter and varies depending on the athlete's skill level, physical capabilities, and running technique. In practice, the following main types of crouch starts are used:

Standard start – the starting blocks are placed at the standard distance, and the athlete's position is optimal.

Elongated start – the starting blocks are placed relatively farther apart, allowing the athlete to perform a more powerful start movement.

Narrow start – the starting blocks are placed closer together, which allows for quicker movement initiation.

Each of these start types should be selected according to the individual characteristics of the athlete.

Acceleration Phase.

The acceleration phase after the start lasts between 15 to 30 meters, depending on the runner's individual capabilities. Its main objective is to reach maximum running speed as quickly as possible. The movements performed during the initial phase of the start are crucial for helping the sprinter achieve high results during the competition.

The correct execution of the first steps after the start depends on the push-off angle (which should be at a sharp angle to the track with maximum force) and the speed of movement. The runner begins the initial steps in a bent position and, from the 6 -7 step onwards, gradually starts to straighten the body. In the acceleration phase, gradually raising the body is very important, as it allows for an optimal start and enables the runner to increase speed as quickly as possible. When the body is in a slightly

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4

bent position, the step of the leg that is about to strike the ground aligns, moving at a 90° angle relative to the pushing leg. This allows the inertia force to be directed forward and optimizes the runner's speed acquisition.

The runner takes the first steps by placing the foot down and backward while pushing the body forward. This movement, along with the quick convergence of the thighs, should be executed as fast as possible, as the quicker it is performed, the more agile and efficient the subsequent push-off will be.

Running Over the Distance.

During running, the angle of body tilt relative to the vertical is about $10-15^\circ$. This tilt changes dynamically throughout the running process:

In the push-off phase, the shoulders are slightly pulled back, resulting in a decrease in body tilt.

In the flight phase, the tilt increases, enhancing the forward lean of the body.

The soles of the feet move almost along a straight line, which ensures optimal balance and stability.

Reaching the Finish Line

In the final phase of the race, maintaining maximum speed until the end becomes more challenging. Typically, about 15-20 meters before the finish line, speed decreases by around 3-8%.

The key to reaching the finish line is that the runner must try to maintain speed as long as possible and minimize the impact of negative factors.

When fatigue begins, the strength of the muscles involved in the push-off decreases, resulting in shorter strides and a reduction in speed.

To maintain speed, it is necessary to increase the frequency of running strides. This is achieved by enhancing the movement of the arms.

Reaching the finish line involves crossing the finish line, which is marked by an imaginary vertical plane passing through the line.

To reach the finish line faster, runners push their arms backward and lean their bodies forward during the final step.

This technique, known as the "chest leap," helps increase the speed of crossing the finish line.

Discussion

The technique of starting and running over the distance is crucial in a sprinter's ability to realize their speed and strength potential. The athlete's efficient and rational use of muscle strength and energy reserves during the acceleration phase directly impacts the outcome of the race.

The Concept of Sports Technique

Sports technique refers to the way in which the movement of certain body parts is manifested in the performance of sports exercises, described through their external appearance.

In short-distance running, the athlete's running style can vary depending on their technique:

Free or Light

Heavy or Relaxed

Powerful or Intense

Low or High Running Style

To conduct a deep analysis of the technique in short-distance running, the general picture of movements is studied in detail using kinograms. As a result of this analysis, precise quantitative indicators such as movement angles, speed, and displacement of body parts are determined.

However, these descriptions alone are not sufficient. This is because only the external appearance of the movements is analyzed, but this is not enough for practical application.

Internal Structure of Running Technique

When evaluating a sprinter's running technique, it is not enough to limit the analysis to the external expression of movements. This is because movements are a result of the contraction activity of the skeletal muscles, the primary motor engines of the human body. Therefore, in analyzing a sprinter's running technique, it is also essential to deeply understand the internal structure of the movements.

Running technique is not just about the athlete's external appearance; it is closely related to the application of force, energy conservation, and the use of an optimal biomechanical style to achieve maximum speed.

In conclusion, sprinters use various methods during their training process. Among these, the repetition method, variable intervals, interval training, dividing the distance into sections, and steady-paced running are effective techniques for developing the speed and explosive strength of sprinters.

Performing various jumping exercises helps improve the athletes' speed and power endurance, providing a solid foundation for better sports results. Another method to improve speed quality is the use of a special resistance system. This involves using a harness and periodically changing direction, running both forward and backward. This exercise is recommended for highly skilled sprinters who have been training for long periods in short-distance running.

REFERENCES

1. Andris E.R., Qudratov R.Q. Track and Field. – Tashkent: 1998. – 124 pages.
2. Andris E.R. Management of Training in 100-meter Sprint. – Tashkent: 1990. – 109 pages.
3. Jilkin A. I., Kuzmin V. S., Sidorchuk Ye. V. Track and Field (Textbook for University Students). – Moscow: Publishing Center "Academiya," 2009. – 464 pages.
4. Shakirjanova K.T. Foundations of Sports Training in Track and Field. – Tashkent: 2008. – 72 pages.
5. Zelichenok V.B., Nikitushkin V.G., Guba V.P. Track and Field: Selection Criteria. – Moscow: Terra-Sport, 2000. – 240 pages.